

Interview for SaaS managing team

Dear respondents,

My name is **Martin Kanamugire**, a master's student at INES Ruhengeri. I am doing a **master's in entrepreneurship development and management**. For partial fulfilment of my master's, I am conducting research in the software as a service business, under the topic *“The Effects of User-Centric Approach (UCA) on Customer Acquisition, Retention, and Satisfaction (CARS) for a Software as a Service (SaaS) Start-up in Rwanda.”* As I chose

Academic Bridge as my case study, I request your cooperation in answering the following questions. The study is only for academic purposes, and it is part of the requirements that will enable me to complete our degree program. Please be assured that the information from this research will remain confidential.

SECTION A: RESPONDENT IDENTIFICATION

This section includes questions regarding the respondent's identification

Q.1. Position in Academic Bridge regarding SaaS (Mark only one oval).

- Software developer
- School or user support staff
- SaaS manager User
- feedback receiver
- Other:

Q.2. Education level (Mark only one oval).

- Senior 6
- Bachelors' degree
- Technical and professional certificate or degree
- Masters' degree
- PhD

Q.3. Education speciality (Mark only one oval).

- Software development
- General computer science
- Business management
- Human resource management
- General education Other:

Q.4. Gender (Mark only one oval).

- Male
- Female

Q.5. Age (Mark only one oval).

- Less than 20 years old
- 20 - 30 years old
- 30 - 45 years old
- More than 45 years old

Q.6. Experience (What is your experience in SaaS like Academic Bridge?)

Mark only one oval.

- Less than one year
- 2 - 3 years
- More than 3 years

SECTION B: THE EFFECTS OF USER-CENTRIC APPROACH (UCA) ON CUSTOMER ACQUISITION, RETENTION, AND SATISFACTION (CARS)

This section has statements regarding the effects of the user-centric approach (UCA) on customer acquisition, retention, and satisfaction (CARS) in Software as a Service (SaaS). Referring to your experience in SaaS (Academic Bridge or otherwise), please kindly provide a response that matches your opinion assessing the statement below.

The following are elements of UCA to be evaluated on relation to CARS in a SaaS**I. User Research (UR)**

Q.7. Conducting user research helps identify real customer pain points, enabling SaaS companies to tailor solutions that attract new users effectively *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.8. Personal development ensures marketing and product design align with user expectations, improving targeting and increasing acquisition rates *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.9. When products or services are built around detailed user personas, customers feel understood and are more likely to remain loyal (*Mark only one oval*).

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.10. Integrating insights from user research into product and service updates leads to better satisfaction, as users see their feedback reflected in improvements (*Mark only one oval*).

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.11. Accurate personas help streamline on-boarding and support strategies, reducing churn and boosting long-term retention (*Mark only one oval*).

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

II. User On-boarding Experiences (UX)

Q.12. Effective user on-boarding enhances first impressions, which significantly increases customer acquisition rates. (*Mark only one oval*).

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.13. Personalized on-boarding processes reduce early churn by helping users quickly realize the product's value, boosting retention *Mark only one oval*.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.14. Smooth on-boarding experiences increase customer satisfaction by minimizing confusion and frustration during initial use (*Mark only one oval*).

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.15. SaaS start-ups with comprehensive on-boarding programs report higher customer lifetime value due to improved user engagement *Mark only one oval*.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.16. Well-structured on-boarding builds trust and confidence, encouraging long term loyalty and positive word-of-mouth referrals *Mark only one oval*.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

III. User Feedback Integration (FI)

Q.17. Integrating user feedback into product development leads to solutions that better meet customer needs, boosting acquisition rates *Mark only one oval*.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.18. Iterative improvements based on feedback increase product usability, resulting in higher customer retention. *Mark only one oval*.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.19. Continuous enhancement through feedback creates a positive user experience, significantly improving customer satisfaction levels *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.20. SaaS start-ups that implement feedback loops can quickly resolve issues, fostering trust and long-term loyalty among users *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.21. Feedback-driven product updates encourage customers to stay engaged and recommend the service, enhancing both retention and acquisition *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

IV. Continuous Customer Support (CS)

Q.22. Continuous customer support enhances user confidence and trust, leading to higher customer acquisition rates *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.23. Ongoing support reduces churn by addressing issues promptly, which significantly improves customer retention *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.24. Customers receiving consistent support report greater satisfaction due to feeling valued and understood by the company *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.25. Proactive customer support fosters long-term loyalty and encourages repeat usage of the SaaS product *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.26. Start-ups that invest in 24/7 support services experience improved customer lifetime value and positive word-of-mouth referrals *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

How do different elements of the user-centric approach collectively affect the overall customer experience in Academic Bridge’s SaaS?

Q.27. The combination of user research, personalized on-boarding, continuous support, and regular feedback integration creates a seamless and engaging experience that increases customer satisfaction. *(Mark only one oval).*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.28. By tailoring the software to meet specific user needs through persona development, customers feel more valued, leading to higher retention rates. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.29. Effective on-boarding helps users quickly understand the platform, reducing frustration and improving early adoption. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q.30. Continuous customer support ensures any issues are promptly addressed, maintaining trust and loyalty over time. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.31. Iterative improvements based on user feedback keep the platform relevant and aligned with customer expectations, enhancing long-term satisfaction. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

The challenges do Academic Bridge face in implementing a user-centric approach to improve customer acquisition, retention, and satisfaction

Q.32. Limited resources and budget constraints make it difficult to invest adequately in comprehensive user research and personalised on-boarding programs. *Mark only one.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.33. Gathering consistent and actionable user feedback can be challenging due to low response rates or communication barriers with some customers. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.34. Integrating feedback into continuous product improvements requires agile development processes, which may be lacking or underdeveloped. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.35. Providing continuous customer support demands skilled personnel and technology, which can strain the start-up's operational capacity. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.36. Balancing the diverse needs of different user personas while maintaining a scalable and efficient platform can complicate product design and updates. *Mark only one oval.*

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Q.37. Any other comment or suggestion regarding this research and about SaaS development in Rwanda

Thank you for your participation and ideas provided. The information received will strictly remain for the research purpose and be kept confidential.